

IPBES Transformative Change Assessment Data Management Report on the case study database with transformative potential and pitfalls

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Description

The scoping report of the Transformative Change Assessment requests experts to analyze historical examples and case studies of transformative change, highlighting both the possibilities and challenges of achieving a just and sustainable world. This database was developed with the overarching goal of collating studies, projects, ventures and initiatives (collectively referred to as "case studies") that illustrate key elements of transformative change, including challenges, views, structures, practices, strategies and outcomes, as well as the roles of various actor groups. The case studies complement one another in understanding the transformative change process, showcasing different combinations of challenges, strategies and actor constellations. As a result, they demonstrate the varied quality, direction and breadth of transformative processes.

Process overview

Protocol

Elaboration of the questionnaire

First, a questionnaire was created by the assessment experts to document details regarding examples that, as per the respondent(s) of the questionnaire, have either led to transformative change or have/had the potential to do so. The definition of “transformative change” used for this endeavour was the one provided in the scoping report - “a fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values, needed for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, long-term human wellbeing and sustainable development”.

The basic structure of the questionnaire was developed by the experts during the first author meeting of the transformative change assessment in France in May 2022. Thereafter, multiple meetings were held online to decide upon the best tool(s)/platform(s) for gathering the information and questions to be included. Based on these discussions, a Google form was created with multiple questions – both closed and open-ended. The questionnaire was divided into several sections and included questions regarding:

- the region and timeline of interest,
- goals,
- sectors and habitats involved,
- proponents and opponents of the initiative,
- their social, economic, and environmental impacts,
- drivers of change,
- the challenges faced.

Response options provided for closed questions were mostly based on previous IPBES assessments/documents.

The preliminary version of the questionnaire developed by a core team was shared with all the experts in August 2022 to seek their feedback. In this questionnaire, the experts provided a specific list of actors that could promote/oppose change across case studies and developed a categorization of the involved economic sectors, both based on broad categories provided by the summary for policymakers of the IPBES Global Assessment. Based on comments and/or suggestions received from multiple assessment coordinating lead authors, lead authors, fellows and all the co-chairs, an updated version of the questionnaire was sent for yet another round of feedback in October 2022.

Sharing the questionnaire

After addressing all the feedback received and discussions with the IPBES data technical support unit, the project leader and researchers shared the questionnaire

with all the assessment experts and the contributing authors who had been identified by then.

To help the respondents, there were two files - one with a detailed explanation for each of the questions and a “model” response showing how the questionnaire was answered for a particular study. The IPBES data technical support unit also prepared a file detailing the type of answers required (‘long text’, ‘short text’ etc.) and provided guidelines about IPBES standards that needed to be adhered to. This version of the questionnaire was then included in the first order draft of the chapters and was available for review and contribution from external reviewers during the first external review of the transformative change assessment (3 February – 15 March 2023).

Fine-tuning the questionnaire

Based on the feedbacks received during internal reviews, the first external review of the transformative change assessment and several sessions dedicated to case studies during the second author meeting in Costa Rica in May 2023, the questionnaire was further fine-tuned to include more qualitative questions that better capture social dimensions to enrich the information and make the database more representative, particularly with regard to the vision and engagement with practices, structures, and views related to each case. A session on the transformative change assessment’s case studies was also conducted at an IPBES fellows’ workshop in Nairobi, Kenya in May 2023 to improve and discuss the data collection process. The questionnaire (A) then was further distributed to receive more inputs describing initiatives from around the world with transformative potential.

Final database version

A total of 407 responses from 87 contributors have been received. Cases with questionable foundations, insufficient support, or that reflected the author's personal opinion on a global topic or issue were excluded. In this sense, ten entries were removed.

The experts also contacted different authors who inadvertently uploaded the same examples so that they could merge these cases. After reviewing the database for duplicates, six entries have been removed.

Therefore, this database includes 391 responses (B) that represent 614 different references that include grey and academic literature (C). The chapters of the present assessment used the collected data to conduct several qualitative and quantitative analyses. These analyses are described in detail in each individual chapter. Despite being an enormous effort from authors worldwide, the database is not a random sample of transformative change initiatives. Consequently, like all databases, it has its limitations. However, it represents a diversity of economic sectors, habitat types, and regions/countries (see **figure 1**). Such a database is useful for moving beyond single case studies to understand common impacts and barriers across contrasting initiatives.

However, it cannot be affirmed that a certain impact or barrier is the most relevant worldwide.

All the chapters of the transformative change assessment included case studies from this database in their final drafts, highlighting different actor groups.

Figure 1. The database comprising 391 initiatives with transformative potential and pitfalls shows representation from diverse regions of the world.

For detailed information on the data used to produce this map, please visit: https://github.com/IPBES-Data/IPBES_TCA_ch2_visions/tree/main

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR_database questionnaire_(A)	csv	42 KB	Updated version of the questionnaire template
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR_case study database_(B)	csv	1,803 KG	The full case study database
C	3_IPBES_TCA_DMR_extraction related links_(C)	BibTex	646 KB	Zotero extraction of the 614 related links to case studies included in the database